

PROSPECTIVE SOURCES FOR PUMPKIN SELECTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14967371>

Abstract. *There have been conducted some researches based on the use of 82 pumpkin accessions collected from 36 countries, housed within the National Genebank of the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources. The study aimed to evaluate these accessions for early maturity, fruit size, and yield potential. The findings revealed that only six accessions exhibited significant early maturity traits. These included k-1127 ('Super Delight', Japan), k-1147 ('Nameless', Japan), k-1154 ('Eurosvemmerc rook veck', USA), k-69 ('Noya', Mexico), k-159 ('Hereules', USA), and k-354 ('Manti-pumpkin, Kazakhstan). Compared to the standard variety 'Kashgarskaya 1644', these accessions matured 6 to 10 days earlier. For fruit size and yield, five accessions showed notable potential: k-160, k-450, k-1147 (Japan), k-1103 (Mexico), and k-390 (Philippines). The average fruit weight of these accessions ranged from 8.2 kg to 13.24 kg, whereas the standard variety '1644' (k-1644) produced fruits averaging 4.7 kg. These results highlight valuable genetic resources for breeding programs aimed at improving pumpkin varieties for early maturity and higher yields.*

Keywords: *pumpkin collection, specimens, variety, early ripening, yield, large fruit, single plant productivity.*

It is important to suggest that pumpkin has long been one of the most widely used plants in Central Asia, not only as a food source but also in folk medicine. Pumpkin is rich in carotene, which helps improve vision, reduces the sugar levels in the blood, and its seeds are used as an anti-worm treatment. Its juice has calming properties and is recommended for insomnia, while in cosmetology, it helps to maintain the skin's youthfulness. In medicine, it is used to treat conditions like eczema and acne. The fiber in pumpkin, along with pectin, helps improve intestinal activity and cleanse the body of cholesterol. It is also effective in preventing diseases of the kidneys, bladder, liver, and cardiovascular system.

At present time pumpkin is grown in agriculture for four main purposes: consumption, juice production, juicy feed for livestock, and pumpkin seed oil extraction. The pumpkin seed meal, after oil extraction, contains 60-65% globulins and albumins, making it a valuable raw material for the confectionery industry. According to global statistics, in 2021, pumpkins were grown on 3.0 million hectares, with a total yield of 27.832 million tons. The majority of pumpkin production, 78%, comes from China (58%) and India (20%) (21.601 million tons). In Uzbekistan, the total area of pumpkin crops is 9,571 hectares, with a total yield of 180,000 tons and an average yield of 18.8 tons per hectare. Given the growing demand for products rich in nutrients and vitamins in both domestic and foreign markets, it is of great scientific and practical importance to introduce high-yield varieties and establish seed production.

Regarding 2018, it should be suggested that only 7 varieties of pumpkin were included in the state registry, with 6 of them created between 1949 and 1974. Due to the lack of systematic seed breeding for these varieties, they have lost their valuable agricultural traits over the years.

"In order to fully meet the needs of the population in our country, it is required to produce 224 thousand tons of pumpkin products annually [1]. Currently, the number of pumpkin products being produced does not fully satisfy the needs of the population. In recent years, scientific research on the selection, processing, and storage of pumpkins has been very limited [2]. To promote healthy eating habits among the population, it is recommended to consume products rich in biological active substances along with protein and energy-rich foods. Pumpkin is one of the main crops that is rich in healing properties, vitamins, and minerals.

Definitely, creating new varieties of pumpkins that are early-maturing, high-yielding, muscat-type, suitable for processing, and creating varieties that can be used as a feed rich in vitamins and minerals for livestock, as well as large, long-storable, juicy feed products, is a priority scientific direction."

"In order to develop the agricultural sector of the Republic, the tasks outlined in the Resolution CMR-845 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated October 18, 2017, on strengthening the feed base of the livestock and fisheries sectors, include ensuring the population's access to affordable, high-quality pumpkin products, creating new varieties that are resistant to stress factors, organizing primary and variety seed production, and implementing them into production. These are among the most pressing scientific and practical issues of today and this research work will serve, to some extent, in the implementation of the specified tasks."

"The research was conducted by the Department of Vegetable and Melon Crop Genetic Resources of the Scientific Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources at the institute's scientific-experimental farm, focusing primarily on the analytical selection method and single-cross breeding to create a new variety of pumpkin with large fruits, high productivity, and suitability as juicy feed for livestock.

Certainly, pumpkin belongs to the Cucurbitaceae family. The Cucurbitaceae family is one of the largest families of angiosperms, containing 103 genera and nearly 1100 species. Most of these plants are found in tropical and subtropical regions, with only a few species occurring in temperate climates. This family has a very broad ecological range, with representatives found in both humid tropical forests and arid deserts. Plants of the Cucurbitaceae family are mostly annual or perennial herbaceous plants that spread along the ground or climb on vines. Shrubby or semi-shrubby forms are rare.

Currently, the National Gene fund of the Scientific Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources houses 1120 live samples of pumpkin collected from more than 70 countries worldwide. We conducted scientific research using 82 samples from this collection. For our research, we used "Kashgarskaya 1644" (K-1644) variety, which was registered in 1944 and is widely grown in almost all regions of the country. The growth period of this variety is 140 days, with an average fruit weight of 4.7 kg and an average yield of 269.8 c/ha."

"The 82 collection samples involved in the research originate from 36 countries around the world, including: the USA, Mexico, Peru, Chile, Argentina, Colombia, Central Asia, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Armenia, Bulgaria, the Netherlands, Germany, Romania, Iran, Turkey, Iraq, Western China, India, Pakistan, Japan, Laos, Vietnam, Indonesia, Morocco, Somalia, Syria and they were studied in-depth in Tashkent region under local soil and climatic conditions based on their key valuable agricultural traits.

During the three years of research, a total of 6 samples were selected based on the early ripening trait: K-1127, "Super Delight" (Japan); K-1147, "Nameless" (Japan); K-1154,

"Eurosvenmerc rook veck" (USA); K-69, "Noya" (Mexico); K-159, "Hereules" (USA); and K-354, "Manti-pumpkin" (Kazakhstan). Among these, the K-69 "Noya" (Mexico) and K-159 "Hereules" (USA) samples were found to ripen 10 days earlier compared to "Kashgarskaya 1644" standard variety, while the K-1127 "Super Delight-1" (Japan), K-1147 "Nameless" (Japan), K-1154 "Eurosvenmerc rook veck" (USA), and K-354 "Manti-pumpkin" (Kazakhstan) samples ripened 5-6 days earlier (as shown in Table 1).

While comparing the selected samples based on the early ripening trait with the standard variety in terms of plant productivity and fruit size, the K-1147 "Nameless" (Japan) and K-1127 "Super Delight-1" (Japan) samples showed a higher yield, ranging from 0.9 to 5.2 and 0.8 to 7.7 kilograms, respectively. However, the K-159 "Hereules" (USA), K-1154 "Eurosvenmerc rook veck" (USA), K-69 "Noya" (Mexico), and K-354 "Manti-pumpkin" (Kazakhstan) samples showed lower results compared to the standard in all indicators." (Table 1).

Table 1: Valuable agricultural traits of the selected pumpkin samples based on early ripening character

Catalog number	Sample name	Origin	Growing Period (Days)	Yield per Plant (kg)	Average Fruit Weight (kg)
κ-1644	Kashgars 1644, st.	Uzbekistan	140	6,40	4,7
κ-1147	Nameless	Japan	136	11,60	12,4
κ-1127	Super Delight-1	Japan	135	7,30	5,5
κ-159	Hereules	USA	130	5,83	3,5
κ-354	Manti-pumpkin	Kazakhstan	136	4,40	2,3
κ-1154	Eurosvenmerc rook veck	USA	135	3,72	2,8
κ-69	Noya	Mexico	130	3,38	2,3

In selecting large fruits from the collection samples, the total weight of the fruits was calculated by dividing the total weight of the fruits by the number of fruits.

While comparing the fruit size of the 82 samples to the standard variety, it was found that 25 samples (with fruit weights ranging from 5.0 to 11.6 kg) had large fruits, 53 samples (with fruit weights ranging from 1.9 to 4.2 kg) had small fruits, and 4 samples showed results almost identical to the standard (4.4 kg) (Table 2).

Table 2: Valuable agricultural traits of selected samples based on fruit size (2004-2006)

Catalog Number	Sample name	Origin	Number of Fruits per Plant (pcs)	Yield per Plant (kg)	Average Weight of Fruit (kg)
κ-1644	Kashgars 1644, st.	Uzbekistan	1,36	6,4	4,7
κ-1147	Nameless	Japan	1,00	11,6	12,4
κ-450	Sample	Mexico	1,26	11,3	9,0
κ-1103	Zapal chiko	Mexico	1,10	10,2	9,2
κ-160	Airu vase	Japan	1,40	11,3	8,3
κ-390	Doboyu goeden Sqush	Philippines	1,10	8,8	8,2

The samples that showed the highest results in terms of fruit size are κ-450, "Nameless" (Japan), κ-1103, "Zapal Chiko" (Mexico), κ-160, "Airu Vase" (Japan), κ-1147, "Nameless" (Japan), and κ-390, "Doboyu Goeden Squash" (Philippines), with an average fruit weight ranging from 8.2 kg to 13.24 kg. This is in comparison with the standard variety "Kashgars 1644" (κ-1644), which has an average fruit weight of 4.7 kg.

In terms of fruit size, the average number of fruits per plant for selected samples was as follows:

- k-1147, "Nameless" (Japan) had 1 fruit per plant,
- k-450, "Nameless" (Japan) and k-1103, "Zapal Chiko" (Mexico) had 1.10-1.26 fruits,
- k-160, "Airu Vase" (Japan) had 1.40 fruits,
- k-390, "Doboyu Goeden Squash" (Philippines) had 1.10 fruits.

The standard variety had 1.36 fruits per plant. These samples also showed 1.4-1.8 times higher yields compared to the standard variety.

For the average yield per plant, based on biometric analysis, 17 samples were selected, including:

- k-153, "Kurore W-2" (Japan),
- k-160, "Airu Vase" (Japan),
- k-238, "Bidzen-CHirshin" (Japan),
- k-1127, "Super Delight-1" (Japan),
- k-1147, "Nameless" (Japan),
- k-230, "Plov-Kadi" (Turkmenistan),
- k-248, "Mestnaya" (Iran),
- k-340, "Mestnaya" (Somalia),
- k-65, "Nameless" (North Korea),
- k-450, "Nameless" (Mexico),
- k-257, "Mestnaya" (Trinidad),
- k-258, "Obrazest 330" (India),
- k-390, "Doboyu Goeden Squash" (Philippines),
- k-1076, "Emballada" (Argentina),
- k-658, "Plet Kab" and k-667, "Kust Kab" (Anatolia).

These samples showed an average yield ranging from 7.3 to 11.6 kg, while the standard variety showed a yield of 6.4 kg. Among the selected samples, the five samples with the highest yields compared to the standard "Kashgarskaya 1644" (k-1644) were:

- k-160, "Airu Vase" (Japan),
- k-390, "Doboyu Goeden Squash" (Philippines),
- k-450, "Nameless" (Mexico),
- k-1103, "Zapal Chiko" (Mexico),
- k-1147, "Nameless" (Japan).

The key valuable agricultural characteristics of these samples are depicted in Diagram 1.

Based on the three-year study of 82 collection samples of pumpkins introduced from various countries of the world, 10 samples were selected based on complex characteristics. These samples include:

- k-230, "Plov-pumpkin(Turkmenistan),
- k-238, "Bidzen-Chirshin" (Japan),
- k-1127, "Super Delight-1" (Japan),
- k-1147, "Nameless" (Japan),
- k-248, "Local" (Iran),
- k-340, "Local" (Somalia),
- k-450, "Nameless" (Mexico),
- k-1103, "Nameless" (Mexico),
- k-658, "Plet kab" (Anatolia),
- k-667, "Kust kab" (Anatolia).

Diagram 1: Key agricultural characteristics of the samples with the highest average yield per plant

This describes the 10 selected pumpkin varieties based on their performance over three years, which are being compared in the following diagram.

Table 3: Key agricultural traits of selected pumpkin varieties from the global gene pool

N.	Catalogue number	Sample name	Origin	Average Fruit Weight (kg)	Yield per Plant (kg)	Yield (c/ha)
1	к-1644	Kashgar 1644, st	Uzbekistan	4,7	6,40	282,3
2	к-1147	Nameless	Japan	12,4	11,60	510,0
3	к-667	Kust kab	Minor Asia	8,5	13,90	482,7
4	к-238	Bidzen-Chirshin	Japan	6,7	10,90	478,5
5	к-340	Local	Somali	8,0	10,50	463,5
6	к-1103	Nameless	Mexico	9,2	10,20	450,9
7	к-658	Plet kab	Minor Asia	8,8	12,17	422,7
8	к-450	Nameless	Mexico	9,0	11,33	393,5
9	к-248	Local	Iran	7,2	8,70	383,5
10	к-230	Plov-pumpkin	Turkmanistan	5,7	7,90	351,1
11	к-1127	Super Delight-1	Japan	5,5	7,30	319,4

Among the selected samples based on complex traits, one sample is from Turkmenistan (k-230), with an average yield of 351.1 c/ha, which is 68.8 c/ha higher compared to the standard variety. Three samples are from Japan (k-238, k-1127, k-1147), with average yields of 196.15, 37.1, and 227.7 c/ha, respectively, all higher than the standard. The yield of the sample from Iran (k-248) is 383.5 c/ha, 101.2 c/ha higher than the standard, while the sample from Somalia (k-340) has a yield of 463.5 c/ha, which is 181.2 c/ha higher than the standard. The sample from Mexico, k-450, has an average yield of 393.5 c/ha, and k-1103 from Mexico has a yield of 450.9 c/ha, showing a yield increase of 101.2 to 168.6 c/ha compared to the standard (Diagram 2).

By summarising it should be suggested that the average yield of the samples from the Small Asia region (k-658, k-667) was 422.74 and 510 c/ha, respectively, showing a higher yield by 140.4–200.4 c/ha compared to the standard variety. It was also noted that these samples had higher results in terms of fruit size and yield per plant compared to the standard variety, where the selection process continues based on these selected prospective sources.

Diagram-2.

Valuable agricultural traits of the samples with the highest results based on complex traits from the global pumpkin gene pool.

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